

A proof of the non-existence of "Samma".

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Introduction: If $\prod_{i=1}^k p_i^{r_i}$ is the prime factorization of the natural number $n \geq 2$, then it is easy to verify that

$$S(n) = S\left(\prod_{i=1}^k p_i^{r_i}\right) = \max\{S(p_i^{r_i})\}_{i=1}^k.$$

From this formula we see that it is essential to determine $S(p^r)$, where p is a prime and r is a natural number.

Legendres formula states that

$$(1) \quad n! = \prod_{i=1}^k p_i^{\sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \lfloor n/p_i^m \rfloor}.$$

The definition of the Smarandache function tells us that $S(p^r)$ is the least natural number such that $p^r \mid (S(p^r))!$. Combining this definition with (1), it is obvious that $S(p^r)$ must satisfy the following two inequalities:

$$(2) \quad \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left\lfloor \frac{S(p^r)-1}{p^k} \right\rfloor < r \leq \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left\lfloor \frac{S(p^r)}{p^k} \right\rfloor.$$

This formula (2) gives us a lower and an upper bound for $S(p^r)$, namely

$$(3) \quad (p-1)r + 1 \leq S(p^r) \leq pr.$$

It also implies that p divides $S(p^r)$, which means that

$$S(p^r) = p(r-i) \text{ for a particular } 0 \leq i \leq \left\lfloor \frac{r-1}{p} \right\rfloor.$$

"Samma": Let $T(n) = 1 - \log(S(n)) + \sum_{i=2}^n \frac{1}{S(i)}$ for $n \geq 2$. I intend to prove that $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} T(n) = \infty$, i.e. "Samma" does not exist.

First of all we define the sequence $p_1 = 2$, $p_2 = 3$, $p_3 = 5$ and $p_n =$ the n th prime.

Next we consider the natural number p_m^n . Now (3) gives us that

$$\begin{aligned}
S(p_i^k) &\leq p_i k \quad \forall i \in \{1, \dots, m\} \text{ and } \forall k \in \{1, \dots, n\} \\
&\Downarrow \\
\frac{1}{S(p_i^k)} &\geq \frac{1}{p_i k} \\
&\Downarrow \\
\sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{1}{S(p_i^k)} &\geq \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{1}{p_i k} = \left(\sum_{i=1}^m \frac{1}{p_i} \right) \cdot \left(\sum_{k=1}^n \frac{1}{k} \right) \\
&\Downarrow \\
(4) \quad \sum_{k=2}^{p_m^n} \frac{1}{S(k)} &\geq \left(\sum_{k=1}^m \frac{1}{p_k} \right) \cdot \left(\sum_{k=1}^n \frac{1}{k} \right)
\end{aligned}$$

since $S(k) > 0$ for all $k \geq 2$, $p_a^b \leq p_m^n$ whenever $a \leq m$ and $b \leq n$ and $p_a^b = p_c^d$ if and only if $a = c$ and $b = d$.

Futhermore $S(p_m^n) \leq p_m n$, which implies that $-\log S(p_m^n) \geq -\log(p_m n)$ because $\log x$ is a strictly increasing function in the intervall $[2, \infty)$. By adding this last inequality and (4), we get

$$\begin{aligned}
T(p_m^n) &= 1 - \log(S(p_m^n)) + \sum_{i=2}^{p_m^n} \frac{1}{S(i)} \geq 1 - \log(p_m n) + \left(\sum_{k=1}^m \frac{1}{p_k} \right) \cdot \left(\sum_{k=1}^n \frac{1}{k} \right) \\
&\Downarrow \\
T(p_m^{p_m}) &\geq 1 - \log(p_m^2) + \left(\sum_{k=1}^m \frac{1}{p_k} \right) \cdot \left(\sum_{k=1}^{p_m} \frac{1}{k} \right) \quad (n = p_m) \\
&\Downarrow \\
T(p_m^{p_m}) &\geq 1 + 2 \left(-\log p_m + \sum_{k=1}^{p_m} \frac{1}{k} \right) + \left(-2 + \sum_{k=1}^m \frac{1}{p_k} \right) \cdot \left(\sum_{k=1}^{p_m} \frac{1}{k} \right) \\
&\Downarrow \\
\lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} T(p_m^{p_m}) &\geq 1 + 2 \cdot \lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} \left(-\log p_m + \sum_{k=1}^{p_m} \frac{1}{k} \right) + \lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} \left[\left(-2 + \sum_{k=1}^m \frac{1}{p_k} \right) \cdot \left(\sum_{k=1}^{p_m} \frac{1}{k} \right) \right] \\
&= 1 + 2 \cdot \lim_{p_m \rightarrow \infty} \left(-\log p_m + \sum_{k=1}^{p_m} \frac{1}{k} \right) + \lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} \left[\left(-2 + \sum_{k=1}^m \frac{1}{p_k} \right) \cdot \left(\sum_{k=1}^{p_m} \frac{1}{k} \right) \right] \\
&= 1 + 2\gamma + \lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} \left(-2 + \sum_{k=1}^m \frac{1}{p_k} \right) \cdot \lim_{p_m \rightarrow \infty} \left(\sum_{k=1}^{p_m} \frac{1}{k} \right) \quad (\gamma = \text{Euler's constant}) \\
&= \infty
\end{aligned}$$

since both $\sum_{k=1}^t \frac{1}{k}$ and $\sum_{k=1}^t \frac{1}{p_k}$ diverges as $t \rightarrow \infty$. In other words, $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} T(n) = \infty$. $\square$